

Review

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Primary thermometry below 25 K: a decade of low-uncertainty measurements linked to the new kelvin

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In 2019, the basic unit of thermodynamic temperature, the kelvin, was redefined by fixing the value of the Boltzmann constant, opening new avenues for implementing and disseminating the kelvin with lower uncertainty, especially at temperatures below 25 K. In response, the *Mise en Pratique* for the definition of the kelvin (*MeP-K*) (2019) has recommended several primary thermometry methods, including acoustic gas thermometry (AGT), dielectric-constant gas thermometry (DCGT), refractive index gas thermometry (RIGT) and Johnson noise thermometry (JNT), as viable alternatives for realizing and disseminating the kelvin. Since the International System of Units (SI) revolution, significant progress on implementing the new kelvin has been made below 25 K. This progress indicates that primary thermometry, particularly its relative variants, can offer promising practical options for realizing and disseminating thermodynamic

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temperature directly linking to the new kelvin below 25 K with lower uncertainty. This is very important for metrological applications of science and industry, which require precise and accurate temperature calibrations.

This article is part of the Theo Murphy meeting issue ‘The redefined kelvin: progress and prospects’.

1. Introduction

Since 2019, the base units of the International System of Units (SI) have been redefined using fundamental physical constants. This marks one of the most significant changes to the metric system since the French Revolution [1]. For thermodynamic temperature, the kelvin (symbol: K) is now defined by fixing the value of the Boltzmann constant. Before this redefinition, the kelvin was defined as $1/273.16$ of the thermodynamic temperature of the triple point of water, which was fixed at exactly 273.16 K [2]. As a result, all other thermodynamic temperatures had to be measured relative to that single reference point. This former definition posed challenges in achieving high-accuracy measurements, especially at extremely low and extremely high temperatures. The 2019 redefinition eliminates the dependence on a single reference point and opens the door to accurate primary thermometry over a much broader temperature range. According to the latest *Mise en Pratique* for the definition of the kelvin (*MeP-K*), this change allows for better accuracy, particularly below approximately 20 K and above 1300 K [3].

The complexity involved in realizing the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) below 25 K further illustrates the benefits of the new definition and of the *MeP-K*. In practice, no laboratory today realizes the ITS-90 in that range as originally recommended. For example, no laboratory currently measures the vapour pressure of hydrogen at 17 or 20.3 K, and no laboratory continues to use constant volume gas thermometry between 25 and 3 K. Today, national metrology laboratories around the world rely mainly on calibrated resistance thermometers, i.e. wire-based temperature scales, except several labs [4–6]. This situation is becoming problematic because these special thermometers are no longer easily available. Moreover, their long-term reliability depends on how they are used. Recalibration is necessary, but it leads to another issue: each recalibration against other resistance thermometers increases the uncertainty of the instrument, reducing its overall usefulness over time.

To address these limitations, the *MeP-K* recommends several primary thermometry methods as alternatives to those prescribed in the ITS-90. These include acoustic gas thermometry (AGT), dielectric-constant gas thermometry (DCGT), refractive index gas thermometry (RIGT) and Johnson noise thermometry (JNT). These techniques offer simplified realizations and improved measurement accuracy. Since the SI revolution, researchers at the Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d’Essais-Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers (LNE-CNAM), France, the Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRiM), Italy, the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Germany, the National Research Council Canada (NRC), Canada and the Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry (TIPC) of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (TIPC-CAS), China, have made significant progress in realizing the redefined kelvin at temperatures below 25 K by primary thermometry methods [7–14]. Figure 1 shows the standard uncertainties of thermodynamic temperature, $u(T)$, measured in recent experiments. It also includes an example of the dissemination uncertainty of the ITS-90, $u(T_{90})$, as maintained at TIPC-CAS below 25 K using wire-scale references. These data make it clear that $u(T)$ can now exceed the performance of $u(T_{90})$.

This progress opens up a good strategy considering a complete shift from T_{90} to direct thermodynamic temperature measurements, which would simplify practical applications by eliminating the need for intermediary scales. However, to support this shift, additional work is needed. In particular, it is essential to confirm the consistency and reproducibility of

Figure 1. Uncertainties realized in the most recent measurements of thermodynamic temperature linked to the new kelvin, as well as an example of the ITS-90 dissemination uncertainties $u(T_{90})$ in TIPC-CAS below 25 K. $u(T)$ data source: AGT(2021) at LNE-CNAM, [7]; Fast AGT(2024)-1 at LNE-CNAM, [15]; Fast AGT(2024)-2 at LNE-CNAM, [16]; DCGT(2021) at PTB, [8]; RIGT(2020) at NRC, [9]; RIGT(2021) at INRiM, [10,11]; SPRIGT(2020) at TIPC-CAS, [12,13]; SPRIGT(2025) at TIPC-CAS, [14]. $u(T_{90})$: reproduced at TIPC-CAS from 5 to 25 K using three calibrated rhodium-iron resistance thermometers, two calibrated by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), UK and one calibrated by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), USA [12,14]. For the meaning of the descriptive ‘Fast’, see §2a.

the different primary thermometry methods. This is one of the focuses in the project titled ‘Dissemination of the Redefined Kelvin’ (DireK-T) launched by the European Partnership in Metrology [17].

The purpose of this article is to present recent advances in state-of-the-art primary thermometry below 25 K, with a focus on direct measurement of thermodynamic temperature that is linked to the redefined kelvin.

2. Principle of primary methods

To implement the new Kelvin scale below 25 K, the *MeP-K* recommends gas thermometry and noise thermometry. Thanks to *ab initio* calculations for working gases like helium [18–24], it is now possible to achieve more accurate thermodynamic temperatures by AGT, DCGT and RIGT, even with a single thermodynamic state, than with ITS-90. In addition, relative thermometry offers an appealing way to measure temperature T with even lower uncertainty, as some effects are cancelled by using the ratio of the measured physical quantity. The principles of these primary methods are briefly outlined below; for more details, please refer to relevant review papers [25–29].

(a) Acoustic gas thermometry (AGT)

The speed of sound in a working gas is a function of thermodynamic temperature T and density ρ as shown in equation (2.1) [25,30–32]:

$$u^2(T, p) = \frac{\gamma_0 k T}{m} \left(1 + \beta_a(T) \rho(T, p) + \gamma_a(T) \rho(T, p)^2 + \dots \right), \quad (2.1)$$

where p is the gas pressure; γ_0 is exactly 5/3 for monatomic gases; k is the Boltzmann constant; m is the average mass of one gas atom or molecule; β_a and γ_a are, respectively, the second

and third acoustic virial coefficients that are accurately determined by *ab initio* calculations for helium [19,24,33].

For the basic principle of absolute AGT, by fitting the speed-of-sound data under different pressures and extrapolating to zero pressure on a single isotherm, one can derive the unknown thermodynamic temperature T from the speed-of-sound under vacuum u_0^2 from equation (2.1), as shown in equation (2.2),

$$u_0^2 = \frac{\gamma_0 k T}{m}. \quad (2.2)$$

The advantage of AGT is that the speed of sound depends strongly on temperature but weakly on pressure, which is a benefit for high-accuracy temperature measurement.

One more convenient choice is the relative AGT, assuming that m and γ_0 do not vary with T , the ratio of two isothermals, T/T_{TPW} , can be determined by [34]

$$\frac{T}{T_{\text{TPW}}} = \frac{u_0^2(T)}{u_0^2(T_{\text{TPW}})} = \frac{u^2(T, p_1)}{u^2(T_{\text{TPW}}, p_{\text{TPW}})} \frac{1 + \beta_a(T_{\text{TPW}})\rho(T_{\text{TPW}}, p_{\text{TPW}}) + \gamma_a(T_{\text{TPW}})\rho^2(T_{\text{TPW}}, p_{\text{TPW}}) + \dots}{1 + \beta_a(T)\rho(T, p_1) + \gamma_a(T)\rho^2(T, p_1) + \dots}, \quad (2.3)$$

where subscript 'TPW' is the triple point of water and $T_{\text{TPW}} = 273.16$ K. By using the ratio, equation (2.3) provides methodological advantages by removing the first-order contribution of systematic error components in the determination of temperature T . More details can be found in [34].

Furthermore, to enhance the efficiency of implementing relative AGT, one can measure T in a relative way at a single fixed pressure, i.e. under isobaric conditions. In this way, the unknown temperature T can be determined from the ratio of speeds of sound against a reference temperature T_{ref} , which is determined by absolute AGT using the same set-up. This is the fast AGT method proposed by LNE-CNAM [15], essentially relative AGT, which significantly reduces the measurement time of a temperature from days to just a few hours compared to the absolute method [15]. Notably, when substituting the parameters $p_1 = p_{\text{TPW}} = p$ and $T_{\text{TPW}} = T_{\text{ref}}$, equation (2.3) degrades into the working equation for fast AGT.

(b) Dielectric-constant gas thermometry (DCGT)

In DCGT, the gas density is accessed by an intensive quantity, the dielectric constant, based on the Clausius–Mossotti equation:

$$\frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{\epsilon_r + 2} = \rho(A_\epsilon + B_\epsilon \rho + C_\epsilon \rho^2 + \dots), \quad (2.4)$$

where ϵ_r is the dielectric constant, ρ is the molar gas density, A_ϵ is the molar polarizability, and B_ϵ and C_ϵ are the second and third dielectric virial coefficients, respectively. In equation (2.4), the density ρ is temperature and pressure dependent, and ϵ_r is measured by the capacitance change of a capacitor at constant temperature

$$p = \rho RT(1 + B_\rho \rho + C_\rho \rho^2 + D_\rho \rho^3 + \dots), \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{\Delta C_c}{C_c} = \frac{C_c(p) - C_c(0)}{C_c(0)} = \epsilon_r - 1 + \epsilon_r \kappa_{\text{eff}} p, \quad (2.6)$$

where $R = N_A k$ is the universal gas constant with N_A the Avogadro constant; B_ρ , C_ρ and D_ρ are the second, third and fourth density virial coefficients, respectively; $C_c(p)$ and $C_c(0)$ are the capacitances of the capacitor at pressure p and in vacuum, respectively; κ_{eff} is the negative effective isothermal compressibility that accounts for the dimensional change of the capacitor owing to the gas pressure.

Combining equations (2.4) and (2.5) to eliminate the density, and substituting ϵ_r with $\mu = (\Delta C_c / C_c) / (\Delta C_c / C_c + 3)$, one can get the DCGT working equation as [35]

$$p = \left(\frac{A_\epsilon}{RT} + \frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{3} \right)^{-1} \left[\mu + \mu^2 \left(\frac{A_\epsilon}{RT} + \frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{3} \right)^{-1} \left[\frac{A_\epsilon B_\rho - B_\epsilon}{A_\epsilon RT} - \frac{\kappa_{\text{eff}}}{3} \left(1 + \frac{B_\rho}{A_\epsilon} \right) \right] + \dots \right]. \quad (2.7)$$

Measuring several absolute pressures and the corresponding dielectric constant on an isotherm, one can get the thermodynamic temperature by fitting [equation \(2.7\)](#) and calculating the first-order slope. Both single-isotherm fit and multi-isotherm fit methods were applied [26,36]. The latter can achieve lower uncertainty by fitting the experimental data from multiple isotherms together. This method (called ‘surface fitting’) was first proposed and applied in the analysis of helium isotherms for deriving virial coefficients [37]. So, DCGT can also be applied to determine the virial coefficients and to compare them with the theoretical results *ab initio* [28,35,38].

With the development of *ab initio* calculations of the virial coefficients, the higher-order virial coefficients from theory can be used as input parameters in the fit to reduce the number of fitting coefficients. Single-state determination of temperature without fitting by combining [equations \(2.4\)–\(2.6\)](#) is now also possible for helium. In recent DCGT work by PTB [8,39], three evaluation methods were applied, namely, the classical evaluation, different-order evaluation and individual pair evaluation; see more details in [8].

(c) Refractive index gas thermometry (RIGT)

The principle of absolute RIGT is similar to DCGT. Thermodynamic temperature is determined by measuring the refractive index of the gas using [equation \(2.8\)](#), whereas the refractive index is obtained from the ratio of microwave resonance frequencies in a metallic resonator measured under vacuum $f(T, 0)$ and at various pressures, $f(T, p)$, as described in [equation \(2.9\)](#). With $n_{\text{exp}} = n_{\text{calc}}$ one can get T with the various virial coefficients determined by *ab initio* methods. This approach is referred to as *direct (p, T) state evaluation* [27]. Alternatively, T can also be determined by fitting data against pressures and extrapolating to zero pressure at a constant temperature, a method known as *ideal gas extrapolation*, which does not require high-order virial coefficients [27].

$$n_{\text{calc}}^2 - 1 = A_n p + B_n p^2 + C_n p^3 + \dots, \quad (2.8)$$

$$n_{\text{exp}}(T, p) = \frac{f(T, 0)}{f(T, p)} \left(1 + \frac{\kappa_T(T)}{3} p \right), \quad (2.9)$$

where A_n , B_n and C_n are functions of T only [27], which can be acquired either by fitting experimental data or through calculations involving various virial coefficients determined by *ab initio* methods [27]; $f(T, 0)$ and $f(T, p)$ are, respectively, microwave resonance frequencies under vacuum and pressure in a resonator; κ_T is the isothermal compressibility of the resonator.

Recent *ab initio* calculations of helium properties have significantly enhanced the potential of absolute RIGT. This advancement has made a third *hybrid analysis* method feasible, where T values are determined for each (p, T) state using literature values of the higher virial coefficients in the ‘*direct (p, T) state evaluation*’ approach [27]. These values are then calculated as a weighted mean or fitted as a function of pressure and extrapolated to zero pressure. However, RIGT still faces challenges related to isothermal compressibility κ_T and measurement accuracy of absolute pressure p . To address the κ_T effect, NRC and INRiM have developed experimental methods and adopted the extrapolation method developed by PTB [40] to improve the uncertainty of κ_T [9,11]. In addition, INRiM has implemented a two-gas method in RIGT, operating at the same temperature and pressure, to mitigate the effects of κ_T [11].

To address both p and κ_T effects, the TIPC-LNE joint lab has proposed a novel single pressure RIGT (SPRIGT) [41]. It is a relative RIGT that operates at a single pressure. In this method, the unknown temperature T is determined by the ratio of the refractive index to a reference temperature T_{ref} using [equation \(2.10\)](#). By using this ratio, the first-order uncertainty

effects of pressure p and compressibility κ_T are effectively cancelled. When combined with advancements in *ab initio* calculations of gas properties for the working gas and high accuracy in microwave resonance frequency measurements [42], SPRIGT holds the potential to achieve highly accurate T measurements below 25 K.

$$\frac{T}{T_{\text{ref}}} \approx \frac{n^2(T_{\text{ref}}, p) - 1}{n^2(T, p) - 1}. \quad (2.10)$$

In addition, another relative RIGT method, i.e. constant RIGT (CRIGT), has been proposed, which operates at a constant refractive index [14]. In this method, the unknown temperature T is determined by the ratio of pressure to a reference temperature T_{ref} using the relationship $T/T_{\text{ref}} = p/p_{\text{ref}}$ in the first approximation. By employing this ratio, the first-order uncertainty effects of pressure and compressibility below 25 K are cancelled, as the dominant uncertainty in pressure stems from the area of the piston [43], and the compressibility of the resonator remains nearly constant in this temperature range [41]. Furthermore, CRIGT avoids potential issues like variable impedance matching in the microwave measurement system. It can serve as a cross-validation method for SPRIGT or be integrated with SPRIGT for T measurements.

(d) Johnson noise thermometry (JNT) (below 4 K)

JNT relies on measuring the thermal noise generated by electric charges in a resistor. When neglecting quantum corrections, the power spectral density $S_V(f, T)$ of the noise voltage V across an unbiased resistor R_0 is proportional to its temperature T . Mathematically, for a given measurement bandwidth Δf , the relationship yields Nyquist's law [44]:

$$\langle V^2 \rangle = 4kTR_0\Delta f. \quad (2.11)$$

If the sensor resistance remains constant over the relevant temperature range, the simple Nyquist formula can be used to determine the thermodynamic temperature T .

Noise thermometry has been used to measure a wide range of temperatures, from below 50 μK [45] to 2200°C [29]. However, the power spectral densities at low temperatures are exceedingly small, making noise thermometry much more challenging in that regime. The development of superconducting quantum interference devices (SQUIDS) made low-temperature noise thermometry feasible [45]. There are three main kinds of low-temperature noise thermometers based on SQUIDS: the resistive SQUID (R-SQUID) thermometer, the current sensing noise thermometer (CSNT) and the magnetic field fluctuation thermometer (MFFT) [46].

R-SQUID thermometers are based on the AC Josephson effect, and their main component consists of a Josephson tunnel junction shunted by a small, biased resistance [29,46]. To obtain a relative uncertainty better than 1%, the integration times of R-SQUID thermometers should be as long as 10^4 s [47], which is why they have been largely replaced by CSNT. For CSNT, 1.5% precision was achieved with integration times of 200 s [48]. Unlike R-SQUID thermometers, a resistor R is coupled in series to an input coil L of a dc-SQUID in CSNT (shown in figure 2). In this way, the noise spectrum of the circuit behaves like a low-pass filter with cut-off frequency $f_0 = (2\pi)^{-1}R_0/L$, and the power spectral density of the noise current is given by [45]

$$S_i(f, T) = \frac{4kT}{R_0} \frac{1}{1 + (f/f_0)^2}. \quad (2.12)$$

In contrast, the MFFT measures magnetic field fluctuations inductively through a superconducting transformer coupled with a dc-SQUID [47] or directly with its antenna as part of the SQUID loop [50]. Because there is no direct electrical connection between the resistive sensor and the SQUID, the MFFT design largely reduces thermal and electrical errors originating from connecting wires and contact resistances [29]. For using the MFFT as a relative primary

Figure 2. Implementations of Johnson noise thermometers based on SQUID current sensors. (a) Schematic diagram of the CSNT [49]. (b) Schematic diagram of the MFFT [45].

thermometer, the power spectral density of the thermal magnetic flux noise can be reasonably approximated by the following empirical equation [50]:

$$S_{\Phi}(f, T) = S_0(T) \left(1 + \left(\frac{2f}{\pi f_c} \right)^{2P_1} \right)^{P_2}. \quad (2.13)$$

The parameters $S_0(T_{\text{ref}})$, f_c , P_1 and P_2 can be calibrated at a known reference temperature T_{ref} . The measured temperature T is determined by the following formula [50]:

$$T = T_{\text{ref}} \frac{S_0(T)}{S_0(T_{\text{ref}})}. \quad (2.14)$$

As opposed to the model-based approach (equations (2.13) and (2.14)), the non-parametric temperature evaluation is an advantageous alternative since it does not require explicit knowledge of the spectral shape of the power spectral density.

A commercial MFFT has been available since 2008 [51]. In addition, a primary MFFT (pMFFT) has been developed by PTB [52]. To meet the demands of primary metrology applications, the design of the sensor and the coil geometry in the pMFFT were optimized for analytically solvable models. For more details and explanations on low-temperature noise thermometry, refer to [29,45].

3. Results and discussion

(a) Acoustic gas thermometry (AGT)

(i) Absolute AGT

After 2019, both LNE-CNAM and INRiM successfully implemented absolute AGT measurements below 25 K. At LNE-CNAM, the speed of sound for helium-4 was measured at the triple point of neon in two separate runs, utilizing five acoustic resonance modes. The difference between the measured and fitted speeds of sound was at the ppm level ($1 \text{ ppm} = 10^{-6}$), indicating a temperature stability of approximately 37 μK . This excellent agreement presents

the good repeatability of the measurements. Ultimately, thermodynamic temperature near the triple point of neon, T_{AGT} , was determined with an uncertainty of less than 0.16 mK and subsequently transferred to a standard resistance thermometer [7].

INRiM has developed a low-temperature AGT system using their RIGT apparatus with the same cavity, specifically tailored for the DireK-T project. With this set-up, $T-T_{90}$ values were determined at low temperatures from 10 to 25 K, which agree well with the $T-T_{90}$ equation established by the Consultative Committee for Thermometry in 2022 [53]. In addition, their findings were compared with other global results at the triple point of neon, where good agreement was also observed [54].

(ii) Relative AGT

Fast AGT has been successfully implemented at LNE-CNAM for temperatures below 25 K, with the reference temperature derived from absolute AGT at the triple point of neon [15]. The uncertainty of T ranges from 0.09 to 0.18 mK between 7 and 25 K. Furthermore, the fast AGT experiment was repeated at several temperatures from 15 to 25 K [16]. Figure 3 illustrates the differences in $T-T_{90}$ between the fast AGT and SPRIGT, demonstrating remarkable consistency with discrepancies confined within 1 mK. The difference near 7 K mainly originates from the different T_{90} data sources across the two metrological institutes. This confirms the feasibility of the fast AGT technique. This results in significant time savings and makes the implementation of the new kelvin below 25 K highly effective.

(b) Dielectric-constant gas thermometry (DCGT)

From equations (2.4)–(2.7), it is evident that in DCGT, the critical factors include the measurement of absolute pressure, capacitance and the correction for elastic deformation of the capacitor. Significant progress has been made at PTB in these areas. For absolute pressure measurement, comprehensive cross-float experiments with a system of multi-pressure balances were performed to reduce the uncertainty of pressure balance measurement from effective areas [55]. Commercially available pressure balances were calibrated against this system for pressures up to 0.3 MPa with relative uncertainties of 3–4 ppm ($1 \text{ ppm} = 10^{-6}$) [28]. For the capacitance measurement, a custom-made autotransformer ratio capacitance bridge was developed [56]. The latest improvement in the capacitance measurement is that the relative change uncertainty, $u(\Delta C_C/C_C)$, has reduced from 5 ppb to 2–3 ppb ($1 \text{ ppb} = 10^{-9}$) [57]. For κ_{eff} , cryo-capacitors were constructed with beryllium copper [28,39]. The elastic properties of the capacitor's material were accurately characterized near the TPW *in situ*, and a new method for extrapolating the compressibility data of solids from room to lower temperatures was developed [40]. Now the relative uncertainty of κ_{eff} , $u_r(\kappa_{\text{eff}})$, has been reduced to 0.2% in the temperature range of 3–300 K.

Below 25 K, PTB has achieved thermodynamic measurement uncertainty below 0.25 mK down to 2.5 K [8,39], and the latest $T-T_{90}$ results measured by DCGT in PTB are shown in figure 4. At a very low temperature (below 3.3 K), a sudden change in the low-temperature properties of gaseous helium has been observed by DCGT [58], indicating that meticulous measurement characterization and careful selection of working pressure are essential in this temperature range.

Figure 3. $T - T_{90}$ comparison between fast AGT at LNE-CNAM and SPRIGT at TIPC-CAS. Data source: Fast AGT(2024)-1, [15]; Fast AGT(2024)-2, [16]; SPRIGT(2021) [13]. Error bar: combined standard uncertainty of $u(T)$ and $u(T_{90})$. The difference near 7 K mainly stems from the utilization of different T_{90} data sources in the two systems: Fast AGT(2024)-1, $u(T_{90})$ better than 0.25 mK from 7 to 24.5 K; SPRIGT(2021), $u(T_{90})$ better than 0.22 mK from 5 to 24.5 K.

Figure 4. The latest $T - T_{90}$ results measured by DCGT at PTB. Data source: DCGT(2017) [39]; DCGT(2021) [8], with $u(T_{90})$ better than 0.19 mK from 4 to 24.5 K. Error bar: combined standard uncertainty of $u(T)$ and $u(T_{90})$.

(c) Refractive index gas thermometry (RIGT)

(i) Absolute RIGT

At the NRC, absolute RIGT was implemented using a racetrack resonator [59], in which the compressibility κ_T of the resonator was derived from other material properties of oxygen-free high-conductivity Cu in the literature [60]. To attain high-precision measurements of T , a microwave-based measurement technique was developed to experimentally determine the compressibility κ_T by applying the RIGT method; κ_T was accurately determined at the triple

point of water ($T_{\text{TPW}} = 273.16 \text{ K}$) using helium and argon as working gases, thereby improving the uncertainty of the resonator's compressibility by an order of magnitude. Then, κ_T at TPW was extrapolated to lower temperatures using extrapolation techniques developed by PTB [40], thereby enhancing the accuracy of κ_T by a factor of 3–8 at low temperatures [9]. As a result, this approach has helped to reduce the uncertainty of $T-T_{90}$ by 14–81% in the relevant temperature range, as shown in figure 5. Given that the RIGT measurements in [9] depend on a known reference temperature ($T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{TPW}}$), the developed RIGT technique is a relative RIGT method.

At INRiM, absolute RIGT was implemented using a quasi-spherical resonator made of Cu-ETP [11], achieving a tenfold improvement in the accuracy of the resonator's compressibility κ_T at low temperatures, similar to the results of NRC [9]. In addition, resonant ultrasound spectroscopy was employed to measure the sample of resonator materials, providing further verification of the measured κ_T . Furthermore, the two-gas method was tested, where the refractive index is measured at the same temperature and pressure for two different gases, such as He and Ne, to reduce the effect of κ_T at higher temperatures. Below 25 K, a thermodynamic temperature uncertainty of better than 0.41 mK was achieved for the triple point temperatures of equilibrium hydrogen and neon [10,11]. Figure 6 shows a comparison of $T-T_{90}$ between INRiM and NRC using RIGT with measurements made close to the ITS-90 fixed points from 13.8 to 161 K, where good agreement was found with differences of less than 0.5 mK, except at the triple point of O_2 close to 54.4 K.

(ii) Relative RIGT

At TIPC-CAS, a SPRIGT system was developed to measure thermodynamic temperatures in the range of 5–25 K [12]. The system consists of three subsystems, namely, for temperature control, pressure control and measurement, and microwave resonance frequency measurement. A cryogen-free cryostat was designed, and temperature stabilities at the 10 μK level were achieved from 5 to 25 K by developing a series of temperature control methods [62–64]. High-stability pressure control methods were also developed by maintaining a piston at constant height to control the pressure through a home-made gas compensation system to supplement the microleak of the piston gauge [43]. The typical relative stabilities are better than 0.16 ppm for pressures in the temperature range from 5 to 25 K. For microwave measurements, a series of methods were developed to improve their stability and accuracy, including closure of the quasi-spherical resonator [65], frequency scanning [66] and precise microwave measurements [42]. A relative stability of 10 ppt (1 ppt = 10^{-12}) level was achieved at low temperatures from 5 to 25 K.

Based on these technical breakthroughs for SPRIGT, thermodynamic temperature T and $T-T_{90}$ results were determined in the temperature range from 5 to 25 K. The combined standard uncertainty of T is less than 0.17 mK [13], representing the lowest uncertainties reported to date in this temperature range. However, before making any comparisons of T , it is essential to verify the reproducibility of the results over several years. To this end, a new experimental procedure, the CRIGT method [14], was employed to measure new $T-T_{90}$ values with an interval of 2.5 years. The comparison results demonstrate that the SPRIGT system is robust. The repeatability of T is excellent with differences of T less than $\pm 0.1 \text{ mK}$, as shown in figure 7. This remarkable agreement further enhances confidence in SPRIGT for implementing the new kelvin below 25 K.

Moreover, thermodynamic temperature T , linked to the new kelvin, was disseminated to three standard rhodium-iron resistance thermometers in the temperature range of 5–25 K, achieving a standard uncertainty of T less than 0.20 mK [14]. The disseminated uncertainty is better than the target standard uncertainty, 0.30 mK, of T from 4 to 25 K in the DireK-T project [17]. This demonstrated the feasibility of directly disseminating T at temperatures below 25 K with the help of the high-accuracy realization of T and the use of highly stable resistance thermometers.

Figure 5. Improvements of $T-T_{90}$ at NRC by RIGT with improved κ_T accuracy. Data source: RIGT(2017) [61], with $u(T_{90})$ better than 0.23 mK from 24.5 to 83.8 K; RIGT(2020) [9] (a relative RIGT depending on a known $T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{TPW}}$) with $u(T_{90})$ better than 0.72 mK from 24.5 to 161.4 K. Error bar: combined standard uncertainty of $u(T)$ and $u(T_{90})$.

Figure 6. Comparison of $T-T_{90}$ between INRiM and NRC using RIGT (a relative RIGT depending on a known $T_{\text{ref}} = T_{\text{TPW}}$). Data source: NRC(2020) [9], with $u(T_{90})$ better than 0.72 mK from 24.5 to 161.4 K; INRiM(2021) [10], with $u(T_{90})$ better than 1.65 mK from 13.8 to 161.4 K. Error bar: combined standard uncertainty of $u(T)$ and $u(T_{90})$. Note that the measurements were made close to the ITS-90 fixed points, thus avoiding the non-uniqueness issues associated with ITS-90.

To extend the application of SPRIGT to temperatures as low as 2 K, a new SPRIGT system has been recently redesigned and built, incorporating two sets of GM cryocoolers and a closed-cycle helium-4 JT cryocoolers. To obtain reliable T_{90} values, three resistance thermometers calibrated by NIST and INRiM were employed. In addition, direct reproduction of the helium-4 vapour pressure scale was also implemented for cross-verification. The initial findings show that the discrepancy between the resistance-thermometer scale and the vapour-pressure scale is within an acceptable range of less than 0.6 mK. Using the NIST-calibrated resistance thermometer as the T_{90} reference, preliminary $T-T_{90}$ results were obtained for both SPRIGT and RIGT methods in the 2helium-4 JT cryocoolers5 K range. Good agreement was found with differences of $T-T_{90}$ less than 1 mK.

These results highlight SPRIGT as a promising method for realizing and disseminating the new kelvin at temperatures below 25 K. Moreover, the SPRIGT method can potentially be extended to even lower temperatures by using helium-3 as the working gas and enhancing the precision of low-pressure measurements in future developments.

Figure 7. Differences of T using different experimental procedures in SPRIGT from 5 to 25 K with an interval of 2.5 years at TIPC-CAS. Data source: T_{Run10} , using SPRIGT experimental procedures [13]; T_{Run19} , using CRIGT experimental procedures [14]. The blue lines denote the standard uncertainty of T_{Run10} [13]. The error bars denote the standard uncertainty of T_{Run19} [14].

(d) Johnson noise thermometry (JNT)

For the project ‘Implementing the New Kelvin’, two primary noise thermometers were developed: a primary CSNT at RHUL [67] and a pMFFT at PTB [52]. In the primary CSNT, the sensor resistance was chosen to balance the lowest achievable operating temperature with the measurement speed. By evaluating all uncertainty components, a relative uncertainty of 1.53% ($k = 1$) was obtained. A comparison of the primary CSNT against a superconducting reference device calibrated with the Provisional Low Temperature Scale 2000 (PLTS-2000) [68] showed agreement to within 1% between 66 and 208 mK [67].

Two separate detection coils, each paired with a dc-SQUID current sensor, were incorporated into the pMFFT. A calibration coil was added to calibrate the signal channels and to measure the electrical conductivity of the resistive sensor. A relative uncertainty of 0.59% was achieved ($k = 1$). A comparison measurement between the pMFFT and the PLTS-2000, provided by a calibrated MFFT, was performed. Between 16 and 672 mK, T_{pMFFT} agrees well with T_{2000} within 1%. However, a slight negative deviation was observed at 15 mK [52]. In a comparison between the pMFFT and a λ -point cell, the pMFFT temperatures showed good agreement with the ^4He lambda point. Furthermore, when operated in both absolute and relative modes, the pMFFT also demonstrated good agreement with the ITS-90 [15].

A direct comparison between the CSNT and pMFFT was conducted by PTB and RHUL from 200 mK down to 200 μK [48], yielding agreement within 0.5% and thereby enhancing the confidence in both methods for realizing the kelvin below 1 K. A separate comparison between the MFFT and PLTS-2000 was performed at LNE-Cnam, showing good agreement from 8 mK to 1 K [69].

4. Conclusion and perspectives

Since realizing the ITS-90 below 25 K is complex, and wire-based temperature scales are not a viable long-term solution, alternative approaches are essential. The redefinition of the kelvin has opened new possibilities, particularly in the sub-25 K range. The *MeP-K* recommends several primary thermometry methods as alternatives to ITS-90. Significant progress in AGT,

Figure 8. $T-T_{90}$ results determined from state-of-the-art primary thermometry below 25 K since the SI revolution. Data source: AGT(2021) at LNE-CNAM [7]; Fast AGT(2024)-1 at LNE-CNAM [15]; Fast AGT(2024)-2 at LNE-CNAM [16]; DCGT at PTB [8]; RIGT(2020) at NRC [9]; RIGT(2021) at INRiM [10]; SPRIGT(2021) at TIPC-CAS [13]; SPRIGT(2025) [14]; $T-T_{90}$, [53]. Error bar: combined standard uncertainty of $T-T_{90}$.

DCGT and RIGT over the past 10 years demonstrates that achieving lower uncertainties in thermodynamic temperature below 25 K is now possible.

Figure 8 shows the latest $T-T_{90}$ results determined by different state-of-the-art primary thermometry below 25 K after 2019. These data were used to produce an analytic function of this difference as a function of the measured ITS-90 temperature T_{90} from 4 to 305 K [53]. One could thus obtain thermodynamic temperature T using a thermometer calibrated on ITS-90. However, more studies of $T-T_{90}$ and $T-T_{2000}$ remain to be carried out and compared to implement and disseminate the new kelvin below 25 K in the future, especially to build a new temperature scale T_{20XX} worldwide based on thermodynamic temperatures traced to the new kelvin.

Recent results show that fast AGT is a highly effective method for implementing the new kelvin. It uses a reference temperature obtained by absolute AGT. This approach achieves uncertainties below 0.18 mK between 7 and 25 K, while also reducing measurement time by a factor of 10 compared to absolute AGT. This makes fast AGT especially useful for calibrating standard resistance thermometers.

DCGT is another reliable method for realizing the new kelvin, with uncertainties of less than 0.25 mK at temperatures below 25 K. This is obtained by very accurate pressure and capacitance measurements, with relative uncertainties better than 5 ppm and 3 ppb, respectively. The development of advanced cryo-capacitors and a universal extrapolation method for κ_T has further improved DCGT; the latter has also been applied in RIGT.

RIGT is an alternative method for realizing the kelvin below 25 K, although its uncertainty is somewhat higher at the moment—around 0.41 mK at the triple points of hydrogen and neon. The main sources of uncertainty are related to κ_T and pressure measurements. To reduce the uncertainty in κ_T , both experimental and extrapolation methods have been developed, achieving a tenfold improvement. To go even further, relative methods like SPRIGT have been introduced. These methods have been used from 5 to 25 K and have achieved uncertainties below 0.17 mK, the lowest reported so far in this temperature range. A repeated experiment using CRIGT confirmed the reliability and performance of SPRIGT in achieving ultra-low uncertainty in thermodynamic temperature. Temperatures as low as 2 K have also been measured using a newly built SPRIGT set-up. These measurements showed good agreement between SPRIGT and RIGT, with $T-T_{90}$ differences of less than 1 mK. This confirms that SPRIGT is a promising candidate for realizing and disseminating the kelvin below 25 K.

There is also potential to extend SPRIGT to even lower temperatures by using helium-3 as the working gas and improving low-pressure accuracy.

To meet the need for reliable and traceable thermometry below 1 K, both CSNT and pMFFT could be optimized further to achieve lower uncertainties. Low-temperature noise thermometry is in progress to resolve known discrepancies in the PLTS-2000 reference data below 20 mK, with the first new results submitted recently for publication.

In summary, primary thermometry has shown strong potential for implementing and disseminating the redefined kelvin at temperatures below 25 K. These methods provide practical paths for direct traceability to the new kelvin with lower uncertainty. This has already been demonstrated by calibrating standard rhodium-iron resistance thermometers [14], which is important for scientific and industrial applications requiring precise temperature calibration.

Now the low-temperature thermometry committee is fully dedicated to advancing the DireK-T project, one goal of which is to expand the DireK-T across the range from approximately 4–25 K and beyond. We also aim to study the feasibility of direct comparisons between thermodynamic temperature measurements and established scales—specifically, the ITS-90 vapour pressure scale below 5 K and the PLTS-2000 scale below 1 K. Such comparisons could eventually be carried out in a single experimental set-up. Overall, these advances may support the development of a next-generation temperature scale traced to the new kelvin.

Data accessibility. This article has no additional data.

Declaration of AI use. We have not used AI-assisted technologies in creating this article.

Authors' contributions. B.G.: conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, writing—review and editing; H.Z.: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; X.K.: data curation, formal analysis, investigation, visualization, writing—original draft; W.G.: formal analysis, investigation, visualization, writing—original draft; Y.S.: data curation, formal analysis, visualization; S.L.: formal analysis, investigation, visualization; F.S.: formal analysis, writing—review and editing; C.T.: formal analysis, visualization; J.Z.: formal analysis, visualization; L.P.: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, validation, writing—review and editing; C.G.: data curation, formal analysis, writing—review and editing; A.K.: formal analysis, writing—review and editing.

All authors gave final approval for publication and agreed to be held accountable for the work performed therein.

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